

Open science as a process, not a product: Insights from the CryoCloud JupyterHub communities

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CryoCloud

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Social innovation and data at the forefront

Drive social and technological innovation forward together

Technological Innovation	Social Innovation
Explains 25% of innovation success	Explains 75% of innovation success

Source: Erasmus University: Competition and Innovation monitor (2006)

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Visionary data practices required

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Active engagement of broad scientific and open science communities at all levels

Open science and open-source software for _____ NASA communities

Defining open-source
software values

Models for serving the community

2i2c
the international interactive
computing collaboration

Lessons learned

Ongoing barriers with a
vision for 2040

Slack

Open-source software values in a new technological world

Cloud bottom line: Time and data storage costs money

In order to innovate:

Reduce timelines

Minimize data storage and egress

Every day we wait, costs snowballs

Modernization: A story of sea surface temperatures

Landsat 8

6 Tb of data storage and a weeks-long pipeline

Timeline

>week

+ 1 hour per image

Storage

Bootstrap

Tasks

MGalloway (WMF)

Delapouite

Tools

Six years later: Modernization leads to orders of magnitude less processing time and data storage

Timeline

1 min

Storage

Tasks

Tools

```
Run NLSST algorithm ¶
(12): timing = time.time()
(13): # Define the Landsat STAC catalog location
url = "https://landsatlook.usgs.gov/stac-server"

# For atb correction
basepath = Path('home/jupyter/Landsat_SST_algorithm')
lsatpath = basepath / 'data'
atbpath = lsatpath / 'atbCorrection'
nodoc_path = lsatpath / 'NODC_L2'

WV = "Water_Vapor"

# For search and tile plot for Landsat
satellite = "Landsat"
collection = "landsat-c2l1" # Landsat Collection 2, Level 1 - Includes L8 and L9
scene = ("landsaturs_path", "landsaturs_raw")
gjson_outfile = lsatpath / f'{satellite}.gjson'

# # For scene search and plot
interp = 1
```


COG
CLOUD OPTIMIZED
GEOTIFF

+

STAC
SpatioTemporal
Asset Catalog

Six years later: Modernization leads to orders of magnitude less processing time and data storage

Timeline

1 min

Storage

Tasks

Tools

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Run NLSST algorithm ¶
(12): timing = time.time()
(13): # Define the Landsat STAC catalog location
url = "https://landsatlook.usgs.gov/stac-server"

# For atb correction
basepath = Path('home/jupyter/Landsat_STC_algorithm')
lsatpath = basepath / 'data'
atbpath = lsatpath / 'atbCorrection'
moduc_path = lsatpath / 'MODIS_L2'

WV = "Water_Vapor"

# For search and tile plot for Landsat
satellite = "Landsat"
collection = "landsat-c2l1" # Landsat Collection 2, Level 1 - Includes L8 and L9
scene = ("landsaturs_path", "landsaturs_raw")
json_outfile = lsatpath / f'{satellite}.gejson'

# # For scene search and plot
interp = 1
```


Code

Platform

Data format

Data access

Six years later: Modernization leads to orders of magnitude less processing time and data storage

Timeline

1 min

Storage

Tasks

Tools

```
Run NLSST algorithm ¶  
  
[12]: timing = time.time()  
  
[13]: # Define the Landsat STAC catalog location  
url = "https://landsatlook.usgs.gov/stac-server"  
  
# For atn correction  
basepath = Path('home/jovyan/Landsat_STAC_algorithm')  
isatpath = basepath / 'data'  
atnpath = isatpath / 'atnCorrection'  
nodoc_path = isatpath / 'nodoc_L2'  
  
WV = "Water_Vapor"  
  
# For search and tile plot for Landsat  
satellite = "Landsat"  
collection = "landsat-c2l1" # Landsat Collection 2, Level 1 - Includes L8 and L9  
ctime = ("landsaturs_path", "landsaturs_mw")  
gjson_outfile = isatpath / f'{satellite}.gjson'  
  
# # For scene search and plot  
interp = 1
```

Code

Platform

Data format

Data access

Six years later: Modernization leads to orders of magnitude less processing time and data storage

Timeline

1 min

Storage

Tasks

Tools

```
Run NLSST algorithm ¶
(12): timing = time.time()
(13): # Define the Landsat STAC catalog location
url = "https://landsatlook.usgs.gov/stac-server"

# For atm correction
basepath = Path('home/jupyter/Landsat_SST_algorithm')
lsatpath = basepath / 'data'
atmcorrpath = lsatpath / 'atmCorrection'
nodoc_path = lsatpath / 'NODC_L2'

WV = "Water_Vapor"

# For search and tile plot for Landsat
satellite = 'Landsat'
collection = 'landsat-c2l1' # Landsat Collection 2, Level 1 - Includes L8 and L9
scene = ('landsaturs_path', 'landsaturs_rnc')
json_outfile = lsatpath / f'{satellite}.geojson'

# # For scene search and plot
interp = 1
```

Consolidation and streamlining

Time for iteration

Time to solution

Impact

Modernization doesn't mean one more new thing

Expensive

Confuses users

An enemy of impact

We value consolidation and streamlining

One more thing

Consolidated
& streamlined

Innovation means building
upwards, not necessarily
something new

Flexible tooling means total interoperability

Flexible tooling means total interoperability

Location

Agnostic

Data

Tools

jupyterlab-pasarela

New spaces and organizational models are needed

Cloud computing and ICESat-2 science

Cloud computing and open science concerns from the May 2022 ICESat-2 Science Team Meeting

- Non-intuitive pricing structures, computing options, infrastructure
- Poor documentation
- Costly to use
- Not obviously more collaborative or faster

This didn't ring true to our experience in the cloud!

The International Interactive Computing Collaboration

- **Non-profit**
- **Service provider** for flexible, interactive computing infrastructure
- An R&D team that **contributes back to open source** communities

: A cloud-computing platform with *bumpers*

GOAL: Simple and cost effective managed cloud environment for **training and transitioning** new users to cloud workflows and **determining community best practices**

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ICESAT-2

: A cloud-computing platform with *bumpers*

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CryoCloud JupyterBook

CryoCloud JupyterHub

cryointhecloud.com

- 350+ users joined since launch in Oct 2022
- 12 software and education workshops supported
- 1 white paper, 1 EOS article
- AGU Open Science Recognition Prize
- Published JupyterBook, all content, and presentations on CryoCloud Zenodo Community
- 2 community surveys

Joanna
Millstein

Wilson
Sauthoff

Advantages to a community platform: CryoCloud as a glue for our communities

CryoCloud community feedback integral to building community best practices

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Data needs are the #1 motivation for switching to the cloud

CryoCloud community feedback integral to building community best practices

Data needs are the #1 motivation for switching to the cloud

79% of users are <10 years out of PhD

Different kinds of users in one place accelerates feedback and collaboration

The screenshot shows a JupyterLab environment with the following components:

- File Browser:** A sidebar on the left showing a file tree with folders like 'CryoCloud...', 'Desktop', 'shared', and 'Sentinel.g...'. A search bar is at the top.
- Code Editor:** The main area contains Python code for plotting satellite data:

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(6,6))
image.sel(band='blue').plot()
plt.plot(ISlons, ISlats, color = 'green')
plt.plot(ATMlons, ATMlats, color = 'orange')
```

The output shows a plot of latitude (degrees_north) vs. longitude, with a color scale on the right ranging from 15000 to 40000. The plot is titled 'Figure 4' and includes the text 'band = blue, time = 2019-05-07T14:53:54.971000,...'.
- Terminal:** A terminal window at the bottom displays a warning message:

```
WARNING: No ICDS were found. Either,
- Install a conda package providing a OpenCL implementation (pocl, oclgrind, intel-compute-
- Make your system-wide implementation visible by installing ocl-icd-system conda package.
(notebook) jovyan@jupyter-tsnow03:~$
```

Datasets

Tools and Developers

earthaccess
A Python Library for NASA Earthdata

An open source community ~~ies~~ without boundaries

Empowering our communities to do what they do best

Building together in one direction

Scientific solutions

Closed science

Shared community resource model

Global challenges

Existing barriers and visions for the future

Deliverables needed today

Barriers: Policies, practices, software, or data that made sense a few years ago

2040: Policies, practices, software, and data that make sense in 2040

Barriers: **Policies, practices, software, or data** that made sense a few years ago

2040: **Policies, practices, software, and data** that make sense in 2040

Barriers to cloud usage: Data access and storage

- ▶ Outdated file formats being put up into the NASA cloud **require download**
- ▶ **Many copies** of one dataset on EarthData
- ▶ Two datasets from different DAACs require different passwords/S3 tokens, EULAs, and programmed variables to access

Barriers to cloud usage: Data access and storage

- ▶ Outdated file formats being put up into the NASA cloud **require download**
- ▶ **Many copies** Cloud costs snowball
Every additional step between the user and data is a roadblock
- ▶ Two datasets from different DAACs require different passwords/S3 tokens, EULAs, and programmed variables to access

2040: Zero friction and interoperable data across DAACs

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DAAC collaborations and initiatives move the needle

2040: Zero friction and interoperable data across DAACs

Earthdata Harmony

GIOVANNI

Cloud-optimized data

Data users

Mission

Tools interoperable and compatible with all data

Ideas propagate faster

DAACs closely integrated

2040: Zero friction and interoperable data across DAACs

Tools interoperable and compatible with all data

DAACs closely integrated

A fundamental change to policy

Ideas propagate faster

2040: Zero friction and interoperable data across DAACs

EARTHDATA SEARCH

Earthdata Harmony

Earthdatasearch-Giovanni

Earthdatasearch-TesVIS

Cloud-optimized data

Data users

Mission

Earthdatasearch-Ceres

Earthdatasearch-AppEARS

Tools and DAACs extensions under one umbrella

Barriers to cloud usage: Mission and data agility

- ▶ After Phase A, a mission cannot switch to cloud-optimized archival formats
- ▶ It will take a decade to move away from ____ data format
- ▶ We chose the norm for data formats at the time

Barriers to cloud usage: Mission and data agility

- ▶ After Phase A a mission cannot switch to cloud-optimized archival formats
- ▶ It will take a long time to modernize and open up data at the time
- ▶ We chose the norm for data formats at the time

Existing policies or tooling may be preventing us from modernizing and opening

2040: One order of magnitude faster and more agile mission pipelines (software and data)

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Data designed from the beginning with the end user in mind

Data and open science experts integrated at every mission phase

Policies and tools that **enable changing archival data formats** at any phase or release in mission

SIPS
Next

Modernized? An order of magnitude fewer lines of code

2040: One order of magnitude faster and more agile mission pipelines (software and data)

SIPS
Next

Mission software and data that is responsive to technological advancements

Cloud bottom line: Time and data storage costs money

In order to innovate:

Reduce timelines

Minimize data storage and egress

Every day we wait, the cost snowballs

Barriers: Policies, practices, software, or data that made sense a few years ago

2040: Policies, practices, software, and data that make sense in 2040

NASA surpassing industry in what NASA does best

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Active engagement of broad scientific and open science communities at all levels

cryointhecloud.com

Thank You!

[tsnow03.github.io](https://github.com/tsnow03)

 @tsnow03

 @TashaMSnow

 tasha.m.snow@nasa.gov

Open science values

Intellectual generosity

Intellectual humility

Right to participate in science

Everyone deserves to be treated with dignity and respect

Proper attribution

It is easy to overlook or take for granted contributions from open science

What did we design vs. import?

We stand on the shoulders of those who came before us

The dent a scientist makes at the boundary of human knowledge on any major problem.

matt.might.net

Cost to run a workshop in the cloud

Case study: QGreenland Workshop

Standing up own hub for 1 month

\$4500 for hub

\$75 in cloud credits

Science experts to advise in constraining hub needs

2-4 work weeks - Build and maintain hub

With CryoCloud

\$75 in cloud credits

2 hours to 2 work days - Science and/or tech experts to advise on user & infrastructure needs

Shared community resource model – expertise and technology

: A cloud-computing platform with *bumpers*

Goal: Simple and cost effective managed cloud environment for training and transitioning new users to cloud workflows and determining community best practices

Built and developed for cryosphere scientists by software professionals at **2i2c** to make it possible to:

- Process data faster
- Minimize downloading
- Democratize science

Cryo**Cloud**

: A cloud-computing platform with *bumpers*

- Persistent for (at least) three years
- Small servers (32 Gb / 4 CPU) for all users, option to bring own cloud credits to access larger servers
- New tool development
 - Personal cost-monitoring tool
 - Intra- and inter-hub collaboration tools
- Community surveys, feedback, and guidance to build best practices

Science done in a fundamentally more open way is the future

OPEN-SOURCE
SCIENCE
INITIATIVE

Overview Why Do Open Science? Transform to Open Science (TOPS)

Open-Source Science Initiative

NASA is making a long-term commitment to building an inclusive open science community over the next decade. Open-source science is a commitment to the open sharing of software, data, and knowledge (algorithms, papers, documents, ancillary information) as early as possible in the scientific process. The principles of open-source science are to make publicly funded scientific research transparent, inclusive, accessible, and reproducible. Advances in technology, including collaborative tools and cloud computing, help enable open-source science, but technology alone is insufficient. *Open-source science requires a culture shift to a more inclusive, transparent, and collaborative scientific process, which will increase the pace and quality of scientific progress.*

To help build a culture of open science, NASA is championing a new initiative: the Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSI). OSSI is a comprehensive program of activities to enable and support moving science towards openness, including policy adjustments, supporting open-source software, and enabling cyberinfrastructure. OSSI aims to implement NASA's *Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024*, which was developed through community input.

OPEN (TRANSPARENT) SCIENCE
scientific process and results should be visible, accessible, and understandable

OPEN (ACCESSIBLE) SCIENCE
data, tools, software, documentation, and publications should be accessible to all (FAIR)

OPEN (INCLUSIVE) SCIENCE
process and participants should welcome participation by and collaboration with diverse people and organizations

OPEN (REPRODUCIBLE) SCIENCE
scientific process and results should be open such that they are reproducible by members of the community

Transform to Open Science (TOPS)

From 2022 to 2027, TOPS will accelerate the engagement of the scientific community in open science practices through events and activities aimed at:

- Lowering barriers to entry for historically excluded communities
- Better understanding how people use NASA data and code to take advantage of our big data collections
- Increasing opportunities for collaboration while promoting scientific innovation, transparency, and reproducibility.

The TOPS mission is aligned with recommendations from NASA's *Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024*, the National Academies reports on [open science](#), [reproducibility](#), and [scientific software](#), and the 2021 UNESCO draft [Recommendation on Open Science](#) synthesis report.

Engage in the open science community on the Transform to Open Science (TOPS) GitHub

TOPS. (2021). Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5225076>

Open Science Curricula: **OpenCore**

<https://nasa.github.io/Transform-to-Open-Science/>

Intellectual generosity

Sharing ideas, advancing other's understanding

Reduce competition and enhance collaboration

Intellectual humility

Our contributions are small relative to the body of knowledge

Give and receive criticism with grace

The dent a scientist makes at the boundary of human knowledge on any major problem.

Right to participate in science

Democratizing science

Everyone deserves to be treated with dignity and respect

Objective and constructive discourse

DIVERSITY

of people and perspectives

EQUITY

in policy and practice

INCLUSION

of all voices and visions

Open science values

Intellectual generosity

Intellectual humility

Right to participate in science

Everyone deserves to be treated with dignity and respect

Open science as a process, not a product

Collaborative, reproducible, open science in the
cloud

C. L. Gentemann^{1,2} ,
E. J. Kearns⁹

 ChelleGentemann

Key Points

Science stands at the cusp of a new, open science, cloud-enabled era

Advances in data, software, and computing are enabling transformational, interdisciplinary science, **changing the realm of possible questions**

Deliberately designed open science communities can **advance science and inclusivity simultaneously**

ChelleGentemann

Process massive amounts of data from a \$36 computer...

Chelle-ter in Place @ChelleGentemann

On my kids @Raspberry_Pi running @TeamKano #OpenSource OS I'm analyzing @GCPcloud #cmip6 climate data and @awscloud MUR SST from @podaac. A \$36 computer running processes on both AWS and GCP with over 80 workers and 245GB. #openscience! @NASAEarth

1:18 PM · Mar 1, 2020 · Twitter Web App

...or from your cell phone or on a flight

Julius Busecke @JuliusBusecke · Feb 6

I am analyzing #CMIP6 on the train on MY PHONE!

🙄🙄🙄

Goddamn it, @pangeo_data is amazing! This has literally been the only time I have wanted a bigger phone screen 🤔

```
Example.ipynl x KilledWorkerProblem.ipynl x  
AA ocean.pangeo.io  
File Edit View Run Kernel Tabs Settings  
KilledWor x KilledWor x Dask Tas x  
Testing error with global max calculation  
import xarray as xr  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
from dask.distributed import Client  
client = Client("tcp://10.32.2.137:40423")  
client  
Cluster  
scheduler: tcp://10.32.2.137:40423 Workers: 3  
In 1, Col 1 KilledWorkerProblem.ipynb
```

2 13 66

Replies

Thomas Moore @SurfTasmania · Feb 6

Replying to @JuliusBusecke and @pangeo_data

Nice! That's way cooler than spinning up a @pangeo_data HPC cluster on your laptop from 35,000 feet up. 🚀

Image credits: Chelle Gentemann

Key Points

Science stands on the shoulders of cloud-enabled e

Advances in data enabling transform changing the re

Deliberately de advance scienc

The Digital Watering Hole (in the cloud)

An opportunity shaped by:

- Open, FAIR and CARE Data
- Scalable computation next to the data
- Modular tools for exploration/narrative

Image: [diana_robson](#)

To tackle challenges that

- go beyond disciplinary silos...
- require analysis of *really* big data
- integration of disparate data...
- *participation* of disparate, diverse communities...
- to ultimately connect with society and impact critical decision making.

Early careers, underrepresented groups, and non-R1 academic institution researchers benefit the most

TODAY: A dataset originating with ESA in a streamable format requires downloading from NASA archives because in a .zip

TODAY: 4+ copies of a dataset version on EarthData

TODAY: Two datasets from different DAACs require different passwords/S3 tokens, EULAs, and programmed variables to access

TODAY: A dataset originating with ESA in an optimizable format requires downloading from NASA archives because in a zipfile

- Every additional step between the user and data is a roadblock
- Cloud costs skyrocket

TODAY: Two datasets from different DAACs require different passwords/S3 tokens, EULAs, and programmed variables to access

TODAY: Stage ___ mission not allowed to choose cloud-optimized archival formats

TODAY: It will take a decade to move away from ___ data format

TODAY: Stage ___ mission not allowed to choose cloud-optimized archival formats

- 2 to 3 decades old policies
- If we can serve archival data to the user, then we reduce data copies and time

TODAY:
___ data

from

Today: Everyone *thinks* they are doing open science

For example: “*We need separate {tools, practices} because our users have different needs*”

Siloed

Integrative,
consolidated

Ignores substantial overlap of needs